

Short communication

First record of *Homotropus elegans* (Hym.: Ichneumonidae: Diplazontinae) from Iran

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چکیده

گونه *Homotropus elegans* (Gravenhorst) برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود. به این ترتیب، تعداد گونه‌های گزارش شده

از این جنس از ایران به پنج گونه افزایش می‌یابد.

Malaise trapping during 2013 in different habitats of Kerman province, Iran, resulted in capturing of four species of the subfamily Diplazontinae (Hym.: Ichneumonidae), of which the species *Homotropus elegans* (Gravenhorst) was found to be new to Iran. The remaining three species, *Enizemum ornatum* (Gravenhorst), *Diplazon laetatorius* (Fabricius) and *Homotropus signatus* (Gravenhorst) were previously recorded from this province (Barahoei & Rakhshani, 2012; Mohammadi-Khoramabadi *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Sarafi, 2014). The total Iranian recorded species of the genus *Homotropus* Förster increases to five species.

The specimens are deposited in the insect collection of Shahid Bahonar University of Kerman.

Material examined – 1 ♀, IRAN, Kerman province, Bardsir, Bidkhoun, N 29°36'42.8", E 56°30'22.9", 29.vi.2013-6.vii.2013, leg. F. Bakhtiarynasab.

Diagnosis – Antenna in female 18-20 segmented with ventral surface similar to dorsal surface, multiporous plate sensilla evenly distributed; face strongly coriaceous, distinctly punctate, with central yellow patch; mesopleuron coriaceous, strongly punctate; mesoscutum strongly and densely punctate; forewing with vein 3rs-m, areolet closed; legs orange; all coxae black; femura orange; hind tibia orange, apically black; hind tarsus black; metasoma black, dorsoventrally depressed, tergites 2-4 entirely and tergite 5 partly orange.

Distribution – Holarctic.

References

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